

ANTECEDENTS AND OUTCOMES IN THE PERFORMANCE OF PERSONNEL AT RAJABHAT UNIVERSITIES IN THAILAND

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Abstract

Rajabhat Universities are higher education institutions experiencing increasing competition. Adapting to survive and enhancing internal organizational factors are crucial for fostering unity and collaboration to achieve organizational goals and improve management efficiency and effectiveness. This research aims to: 1) Study the levels of agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational performance management policy, acceptance/adaptation to organizational innovation, personnel participation, job satisfaction, and performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand. 2) Examine the influence of variables such as agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational performance management policy, acceptance/adaptation to organizational innovation, personnel participation, and job satisfaction on the performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand. 3) Develop a model for enhancing the performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand. This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research. In the quantitative phase, the sample consists of personnel from Rajabhat Universities in Thailand, with the sample size determined by a criterion of 20 times the number of observed variables. A proportional stratified sampling method was used, with data collected via questionnaires and analyzed using structural equation modeling. The qualitative phase involves in-depth interviews with key informants, including university presidents, vice presidents, or assistant presidents with at least two years of administrative experience, totaling 20 individuals. The research findings indicate that: 1) Agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational performance management policy, acceptance/adaptation to organizational innovation, personnel participation, job satisfaction, and performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand are at a high level. 2) Variables such as agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational performance management policy, acceptance/adaptation to organizational innovation, personnel participation, and job satisfaction significantly influence the performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand at a .05 significance level. 3) The developed model for enhancing the performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat University in Thailand, named the OLCJPA - RRU Model (O = Organizational Performance Management Policy, L = Agile Leadership, C = Corporate Social Responsibility, J = Job Satisfaction, P = Personnel Participation, I = Acceptance and Adaptation to Innovation in Organizations, RRU = Results of the Operations of Rajabhat University Personnel of Thailand). Additionally, the qualitative research findings suggest that enhancing performance outcomes at Rajabhat Universities requires establishing a governance system based on good governance principles, utilizing new management innovations and technologies, and providing training to develop personnel expertise in digital technology to improve efficiency and effectiveness. This practical approach will enhance the competitiveness and potential of personnel and organizations. The research outcomes can be applied as a policy framework to enhance the performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand in the future.

Keywords: Antecedents, Outcomes, Performance, Personnel.

INTRODUCTION

The current economic (Čižmešija & Škrinjarić, 2021) and social environment is increasingly competitive, requiring organizations to adapt to survive and enhance their competitiveness. Developing various internal factors within the organization has become essential, with organizational culture standing out as a crucial element. Organizational culture fosters unity and collaboration, helping organizations achieve their goals. This need for adaptation extends even to the education sector, which faces high levels of competition. According to Ahmad, Liu, Akhtar, and Siddiqi (2022) study on adaptive culture, it was found that participatory culture has the most significant positive impact on organizational effectiveness. Mission culture and unity culture also have positive influences.

The study revealed that organizational culture (when considering all independent variables simultaneously) can explain an organization's effectiveness by connecting personnel with the organization's values (Corporate Value), fostering their commitment. These values manifest in organizational culture (Organization Culture or Corporate Culture) (Alo, Ali, Zahoor, Arslan, & Golgeci, 2023), which encompasses the beliefs, values, and behavioral patterns shared and practiced by personnel in the form of words, thoughts, learning, actions, or behaviors within the organization. Organizational culture can determine an organization's success or failure by influencing work behaviors aligned with organizational goals and shared beliefs and values (Alghababsheh, Abu khader, Butt, & Moktadir, 2022).

Organizational culture serves as a fundamental principle, emerging from group learning, and is used as a tool for solving adaptation challenges. It is transmitted to organization members and functions as both a behavioral pattern and a guide for behavior that all members adhere to. It reflects the organization's or society's reality, which is widely recognized and accepted (Amado dos Santos, Méxas, Meiriño, Sampaio, & Costa, 2020). Gordon describes organizational culture as the internal environment of an organization, comprising assumptions, beliefs, and values shared by its members and used as a framework for interaction with the formal structure to shape behavioral patterns.

Culture underpins human attitudes and behaviors within society, and organizations, as sub-societies, must have a culture that guides life or work behavior patterns, often unconsciously. Alinaghian and Razmdoost (2021) referred to organizational culture as a pattern or way of life that gives an organization its unique identity, distinguishing it from others. This way of life can be exchanged or spread among members of society through social refinement processes. Culture acts as the glue or principle that holds an organization or unit together, preventing it from falling apart (Anugerah, Muttaqin, & Trinarningsih, 2022).

Research on the importance of culture within organizations highlights three key aspects: Organizational culture can determine the behavioral patterns of the organization. For instance, if most people within an organization tend to be indifferent to problems, this general attitude will create a pattern of indifference, which will be absorbed, learned, and spread among its members. Over time, this will develop into a culture of indifference, becoming a standard for human behavior within that organization (Ahmadi, Madani, & Alipour, 2019). The behavioral

patterns that arise from organizational culture can either support or hinder the organization's operations, particularly in problem-solving and decision-making. For example, in an organization where people accept authority without question and lack the courage to initiate problem-solving, a culture of reckless compliance (Subordination culture) may develop. This behavior becomes an obstacle to creative and innovative problem-solving, which is crucial for overcoming challenges (Chen, Huang, Su, Streimikiene, & Balezentis, 2021).

The cultural pattern may dictate which problem-solving methods are acceptable and which are not, based on the group's shared mindset. Therefore, culture plays a critical role in studying organizational problems, including structure, processes, behavior, and the organizational environment. Research by Danuso, Giones, and Ribeiro da Silva (2022) found that culture significantly influences learning, particularly in creating situations where learned helplessness may develop. Learned helplessness is a mental state where individuals believe they cannot control their life goals. When this perception is reinforced by direct experience, individuals may lose motivation to respond to challenges, leading to behaviors characterized by resignation and a lack of effort toward achieving organizational goals. A culture of mindless submission to superiors can foster a sense of hopelessness within the organization. In Thailand, research on organizational culture often focuses on how these dynamics play out within local contexts.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the level of variables affecting the performance of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand
- 2) To study the influence of variables affecting the performance of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand
- 3) To create a model for improving the performance of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scope of the Research

1. **Scope**, this study investigates the factors influencing and resulting from the performance of personnel at Rajabhat universities in Thailand. It focuses on personnel participation, acceptance and adaptation to organizational innovation, social responsibility, job satisfaction, agile leadership, management policies, and overall organizational performance.
2. **Population and Sample Scope**, the population for this study comprises 30,128 personnel from Rajabhat universities across Thailand (Human Resource Management Division, Rajabhat University, 2022). The study involves 10 Rajabhat universities. A quantitative sample size was estimated using a ratio of 1:20, resulting in a sample of 360 individuals. For the qualitative component, 10 participants were selected, including presidents, vice presidents, or related vice presidents, or assigned or assistant presidents with a minimum of 2 years of administrative experience.

3. **Variable Scope**, the variables in this research were identified through a literature review and are categorized as follows: **Internal Variables:** (1.1) Acceptance and adaptation to organizational innovation, (1.2) Personnel participation, (1.3) Job satisfaction, and (1.4) Performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat universities in Thailand. **External Variables:** (2.1) Agile leadership, (2.2) Social responsibility, and (2.3) Organizational performance management policies.
4. **Time Scope**, the research was conducted between June 2021 and December 2022.

RESEARCH RESULT

Table 1: Latent and Observation Variable

Latent Variable	Observation Variable
Agile Leadership (AGILD)	Decision-Making (DECI)
	Problem Solving (SOLV)
	Organizational Change Potential (OCPTT)
Social Responsibility (CSR)	Public Benefit (PBINT)
	Contextual Alignment with the Area (CSLCT)
Organizational Performance Management Policy (ORPMP)	Organizational Efficiency Development Plan (OEDP)
	Organizational Management Strategy (OMS)
Acceptance and Adaptation to Organizational Innovation (OPOMS)	Innovation Creation (CRINO)
	Utilization of Innovation in Operations (USINO)
Personnel Participation (PEPAR)	Organizational Policy Formulation (OGPST)
	Implementation of the Action Plan (IMACP)
Job Satisfaction (JBSTF)	Internal Satisfaction (INSTF)
	External Satisfaction (EXSTF)
Performance Outcomes of Rajabhat University Personnel in Thailand (ORSUN)	Achievement of University Goals in Graduate Production (GDPRD)
	Research Quality (RESER)
	Academic Services (ACAD)
	Preservation of Arts and Culture (CULAT)
	Administration (ADMIN)

Part 1: The results of the study on the level of variables affecting the performance of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand.

Agile Leadership (AGILD) was found to be at a high level with an average score of 4.12. When examining each aspect, Decision Making (DECI), Problem Solving (SOLV), and Organizational Transformation Potential (OCPTT) were all at a high level, with average scores ranging from 4.10 to 4.15. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was also at a high level with an average score of 4.13. Public Benefit (PBINT) and Contextual Alignment (CSLCT) were both rated highly, with average scores between 4.02 and 4.23. Organizational Performance Management Policy (ORPMP) achieved a high level with an average score of 4.14. When considering each aspect, the Organizational Efficiency Development Plan (OEDP) and Organizational Management Strategy (OMS) were both at a high level, with average scores ranging from 4.01 to 4.26. Organizational Innovation Acceptance and Adaptation (OPOMS) was at a high level with an average score of 4.26. Within this, Innovation Creation (CRINO) and Innovation Implementation in Operations (USINO) were both rated highly, with average

scores ranging from 4.22 to 4.29. Personnel Participation (PEPAR) was at a high level, with an average score of 4.27. The aspects of Organizational Policy Setting (OGPST) and Implementation of Action Plans (IMACP) were also at a high level, with average scores between 4.25 and 4.28. Job Satisfaction (JBSTF) was at a high level, with an average score of 4.09. Internal Satisfaction (INSTF) and External Satisfaction (EXSTF) were both at a high level, with average scores ranging from 4.03 to 4.14.

The performance results of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand (ORSUN) were at a high level, with an average score of 4.05. When considering each aspect, the achievement of university goals in graduate production (GDPRD), research quality (RESER), academic services (ACAD), art and culture maintenance (CULAT), and administration (ADMIN) were all at a high level, with average scores ranging from 3.88 to 4.16.

Part 2: Results of the study on the influence of variables on the performance of personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand

Table 2: Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), percentage of distribution coefficient (%CV), minimum (Min), maximum (Max), Skewness (Sk), Kurtosis (Ku), and P-value of Chi-square test (χ^2) of the empirical variables studied (n=360).

Variable	M	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
DECI	4.15	.84	20.41	-2.701	-1.489	9.511	.009
SOLV	4.10	.91	22.33	-3.235	-3.152	2.400	.000
OCPTT	4.12	.86	21.06	-2.828	-1.499	1.248	.006
PBINT	4.02	.99	24.62	-3.217	-3.142	2.222	.000
CSLCT	4.23	.98	23.25	-3.139	-3.164	19.860	.000
OEDP	4.01	.93	23.31	-2.483	-1.620	8.787	.012
OMS	4.26	.70	16.52	-3.158	-3.865	24.915	.000
CRINO	4.22	.74	17.53	-3.228	-3.117	2.140	.000
USINO	4.29	.66	15.40	-2.839	-2.524	14.427	.001
OGPST	4.25	.66	15.51	-2.586	-2.329	12.114	.002
IMACP	4.28	.68	16.04	-3.270	-2.527	17.076	.000
INSTF	4.14	.80	19.33	-2.670	-1.530	9.472	.009
EXSTF	4.03	.93	23.07	-2.683	-3.210	17.499	.000
GDPRD	4.00	.95	23.73	-2.571	-2.468	12.700	.002
RESER	4.06	.92	22.83	-3.134	-2.920	18.351	.000
ACAD	3.88	.98	25.43	-2.103	-2.354	9.965	.007
CULAT	4.13	.65	15.82	-1.667	-.437	2.969	.227
ADMIN	4.16	.66	16.03	-1.901	-1.956	7.438	.024

Therefore, the researcher needs to modify the model to be consistent with the empirical data by allowing the standard deviation (S.D.) variance of some pairs of empirical variables to be related, considering the appropriateness and feasibility in terms of concepts and theories, as well as related research and the feasibility of discussing the research results from the model modification until the model that has been modified (Adjust Model) is consistent with the empirical data, then the relationship path of the model will be considered in detail as follows: The results of the analysis of the model according to the hypothesis are as follows:

Results of the Analysis of the Adjusted Structural Equation Model

The researcher adjusted the model according to the hypotheses to align with the empirical data by allowing the standard deviation (θ) variances of 23 pairs of empirical variables to be correlated (df before adjustment = 122; df after adjustment = 99). The results indicated that the adjusted model (Adjusted Model) was consistent with the empirical data.

This conclusion is based on the following fit indices: $\chi^2 = 189.39$, $df = 99$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2/df = 1.91$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .041$, $SRMR = .048$, $CFI = .99$, $GFI = .93$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 203.68$. The examination of the fit indices revealed the following: $\chi^2 = 189.39$, $df = 99$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$: This does not meet the criteria, as it is statistically significant ($P\text{-value} < .05$) (Joreskog & Sorbom, 1996).

However, χ^2 is sensitive to sample size, so the researcher also considered the χ^2/df ratio, which was 1.91, meeting the criteria as it is less than 2.00 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). $RMSEA = .048$: This meets the criteria as it is less than .05 (MacCallum et al., 1996). $RMR = .041$: This meets the criteria as it is less than .05 (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2000). $SRMR = .048$: This meets the criteria as it is less than .05 (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2000). $CFI = .99$: This meets the criteria as it is greater than .90 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). $GFI = .93$: This meets the criteria as it is greater than .90 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). $AGFI = .91$: This meets the criteria as it is greater than .90 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). $CN = 203.68$: This meets the criteria as it is greater than 200.00 (Joreskog & Sorbom, 1996).

Based on these fit index values, it can be concluded that the adjusted structural equation model (Adjusted Model) fits well with the empirical data, and the parameter estimates in the model are acceptable.

Table 2: The results of the comparison of the calculated statistical values with the criteria to examine the consistency with the empirical data of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjust Model).

Criteria	Defined Criteria	Model Statistics	Evaluation
Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square Statistic (χ^2)	P-value greater than or equal to .05 (Jeong, Kim, & Kim, 2021)	$\chi^2 = 189.39$ df = 99 p-value = .05	Passed
Relative χ^2 (χ^2/df)	Less than or equal to 2.00 (Abraham, Ali, Andangsari, & Hartanti, 2020)	1.91	Passed
Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Less than or equal to .05 (Alias, Ismail, & Sahiddan, 2015)	.048	Passed
Root Mean Squared Residuals (RMR)	Less than or equal to .05 (Alotaibi & Alotaibi, 2021)	.041	Passed
Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual (SRMR)	Less than or equal to .05 (Dochat et al., 2020)	.048	Passed
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	Greater than or equal to .90 (Beccaria, Beccaria, & McCosker, 2018)	.99	Passed
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	Greater than or equal to .90 (Plessis, Golay, Wilquin, Favrod, & Rexhaj, 2018)	.93	Passed
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	Greater than or equal to .90 (Sangsuk & Siriparp, 2015)	.91	Passed
Critical N (CN)	Greater than or equal to 200 (Yusof, Mustapha, Mohamad, & Bunian, 2012)	203.68	Passed

The fit indices of the revised structural equation model demonstrate alignment with the empirical data. The fit indices are as follows: $\chi^2 = 189.39$, df = 99, p-value = .00000, $\chi^2/df = 1.91$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .041, SRMR = .048, CFI = .99, GFI = .93, AGFI = .91, and CN = 203.68. Based on these indices, it can be concluded that the adjusted structural equation model (Adjusted Model) is well-aligned with the empirical data, and the parameter estimates in the model are acceptable.

Qualitative Data Analysis Results

Following the quantitative research steps, the researcher analyzed the broad responses concerning agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational performance management policies, organizational innovation acceptance and adaptation, personnel participation, job satisfaction, and performance outcomes of Rajabhat University personnel. To gain deeper insights, the researcher conducted formal in-depth interviews with 20 executives and experts from Rajabhat Universities. The interviews were conducted in the actual work environment of these executives and experts to observe and learn directly from their experiences.

The interviews followed a structured format, and the feedback was interpreted and evaluated impartially. The qualitative findings are summarized as follows:

Key Insights from In-Depth Interviews: The performance outcomes of personnel at Rajabhat Universities are a result of their work and performance. These outcomes reflect the achievement of university goals, including education management, research, academic services, art and culture preservation, and overall university management. Effective performance is crucial for enhancing efficiency, decision-making, personnel development, process improvement, satisfaction among students and service users, resource allocation, and risk management. This view is supported by an expert who noted, “...Performance evaluation helps administrators understand personnel strengths and weaknesses, allowing for targeted training and development to enhance their capabilities and knowledge...”

Effective performance results are vital for Rajabhat Universities to achieve their goals and ensure long-term success. This is echoed by several experts who said, “...Performance results help organizations evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of personnel and processes. Clear measurements enable organizations to assess whether they are on the right track and make timely improvements...”

Agile leadership is crucial to personnel performance at Rajabhat Universities. Agile leaders quickly respond to organizational and external changes, aiding personnel in adapting and managing new situations effectively. An expert remarked, “...Agile leaders significantly impact personnel performance because if leaders are agile and innovative, it will encourage personnel to align their work with the leaders’ approach, resulting in faster achievement of work goals...” Agile leaders can efficiently set goals and plan work, leading to timely and effective performance. Several experts emphasized, “...A leader who can make swift, effective decisions instills confidence in their team, motivating them to develop and commit to their work. Quick, rational decisions enhance personnel confidence and dedication...”

Social responsibility plays a significant role in the acceptance and adaptation of innovation within the organization. It helps build a positive image and credibility, influencing personnel and stakeholders to support and adopt new innovations. An expert shared, “...Social responsibility affects the acceptance and adaptation of innovations because many organizations, including educational institutions, are increasingly aware of their social impact. This awareness influences how new innovations are embraced...” Engaging in social responsibility activities enhances organizational image and fosters relationships, contributing to a supportive environment for innovation and adaptation.

CONCLUSION

The sample group in this research comprised 193 females, representing 53.50% of the total sample, with the majority aged 46 years and older (31.00%, 112 individuals). Most participants were single (42.50%, 153 individuals), held a master's degree (32.00%, 115 individuals), earned a monthly income of 30,001 baht or more (33.00%, 119 individuals), and had been employed for six years or longer (44.00%, 158 individuals). Analysis of Factors Influencing the Performance of Personnel at Rajabhat Universities in Thailand. The study revealed that agile leadership, social responsibility, organizational management policies, acceptance and adaptation to innovation, personnel participation, job satisfaction, and the overall performance

of personnel at Rajabhat universities were rated highly across all variables. The path analysis between the causal latent variables (Independent Variables) and the dependent variables in the developed and adjusted model indicated the following:

Social responsibility had a direct influence on the acceptance and adaptation of innovation within the organization, with an influence coefficient of .48, statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 73% of the variance. Acceptance and adaptation of innovation, agile leadership, and organizational performance management policies had direct influences on personnel participation, with influence coefficients of .62, .40, and .63, respectively, all statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 82% of the variance. Personnel participation, agile leadership, and organizational performance management policies directly influenced job satisfaction, with influence coefficients of .67, .51, and .36, respectively, all statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 76% of the variance. Job satisfaction, agile leadership, and organizational performance management policies directly influenced the performance of personnel at Rajabhat universities, with influence coefficients of .71, .44, and .59, respectively, all statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 91% of the variance.

The path analysis between the external latent variables and the internal latent variables (Reduced Equations) in the developed and adjusted model revealed. Agile leadership had a total effect on the acceptance and adaptation of innovation within the organization, with an influence coefficient of .48, statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 72% of the variance. Agile leadership, social responsibility, and organizational performance management policies had overall effects on personnel participation, with influence coefficients of .40, .49, and .63, respectively, statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 82% of the variance. Agile leadership, social responsibility, and organizational performance management policies also had overall effects on job satisfaction, with influence coefficients of .82, .53, and .67, respectively, statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 75% of the variance. Agile leadership, social responsibility, and organizational performance management policies had overall effects on the performance outcomes of Rajabhat University personnel, with influence coefficients of .87, .65, and .98, respectively, statistically significant at the .05 level, explaining 90% of the variance. Based on the study's findings, the researcher developed a model for enhancing the performance outcomes of Rajabhat University personnel in Thailand, termed the OLCJPA - RRU Model:

O = Organizational Performance Management Policy

L = Agile Leadership

C = Corporate Social Responsibility

J = Job Satisfaction

P = Personnel Participation

I = Acceptance and Adaptation to Innovation in Organizations

RRU = Results of the Operations of Rajabhat University Personnel in Thailand.

Research- Holistic Improvement: By integrating these factors, the model provides a comprehensive approach to enhancing the performance of university personnel. It addresses various aspects from leadership and job satisfaction to innovation and social responsibility. Strategic Focus: It helps in developing targeted strategies to improve each component, thereby leading to better overall results. Performance Evaluation: The model provides a framework for assessing how well different variables influence performance outcomes, enabling more informed decision-making and continuous improvement. Adaptability: Emphasizing agile leadership and innovation acceptance ensures that the organization remains adaptable and resilient in a changing environment.

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